

D7.4: Online Rating Repository

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ABSTRACT:	This deliverable presents the Online Rating Repository as specified and implemented on the XR4Human website: XR4Human Rating Repository. The Rating Repository is organized into four main sections: (1) the XR4Human Code of Conduct; (2) a guide for understanding and applying the XR4Human Code of Conduct; (3) three tools for implementing the Code of Conduct, namely the XR4Human Compliance Checklist, Ethical Impact Assessment, and AI Guide; and (4) six thematic sections. This deliverable provides explanations and guidance on the usage of the Online Rating Repository sections, guides and tools.
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1 Introduction

The XR4Human Rating Repository is a webpage that serves as a central online hub supporting the ethical and human-centred development of immersive technologies. It combines a conceptual framework with a range of practical tools that help users understand, apply, and operationalize the principles of the XR4Human Code of Conduct when developing or evaluating XR applications.

The content is based on the XR4Human Code of Conduct and other deliverables generated during the XR4Human project. In addition to establishing a solid XR ethics foundation, it provides guides and tools for empowering European XR stakeholders in assessing and rating their XR software and hardware solutions. Through its focus on Ethics, Interoperability, Legal and Regulatory Aspects, as well as the Experience Library, the XR4Human Rating Repository provide a set of comprehensive entry points that help European stakeholders navigate the complexity of XR ethics.

The XR4Human Rating Repository is designed to be used in flexible and sustainable ways, either standalone or in conjunction with other knowledge bases and tools, such as Openverse Observatory and the EU AI Act.

1 Overview of the Online Rating Repository

The XR4Human Rating Repository was designed to provide a clear, accessible, and user-friendly environment that brings together key information, tools, and resources. The aim was to create an integrated page where users can easily navigate through the repository, minimize unnecessary navigation steps, and allow users to explore content seamlessly. The layout was optimized for accessibility and responsiveness, ensuring consistent performance and readability across all screen sizes, including mobile devices as small as 360 pixels wide.

The Rating Repository is organized with a short introductory section, presenting the purpose and objective of the Rating Repository, and the following main sections:

1. The XR4Human Code of Conduct for the human-centred and ethical development of immersive technologies
2. Four guided steps: Learn, Assess, Test & Explore, Reflect
3. Three tools designed to operationalize the XR4Human Code of Conduct: the XR4Human Compliance Checklist, the Ethical Impact Assessment, and the AI Guide
4. Six thematic sections: Interoperability, Ethics, Legal/Policy, Education, Experience Library, and Forum.

The aim of the four guided steps – Learn, Assess, Test & Explore, and Reflect – is to act as a roadmap, helping users understand how to navigate the repository, explore the content, and make use of the available tools. Each step links directly to relevant sections, allowing users to move between the learning resources, the assessment tools, and interactive spaces such as the XR4Human Experience Library and the XR4Human Forum. All the above components, the XR4Human Code of Conduct, the assessment tools, the learning resources, and the interactive spaces are explained hereafter.

2 Code of Conduct (WP5)

An essential component of the Rating Repository is the XR4Human Code of Conduct (D5.2). The XR4Human Code of Conduct sets forth the ethical obligations for developers involved in technological innovation and governance of immersive technologies, including Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Mixed Reality (MR), as well as all current and other emerging immersive environments. The Code is designed to ensure that these technologies respect human rights, protect user privacy, promote inclusivity, and safeguard the mental, physical, and social well-being of all users.

The Code of Conduct serves as a reference for the users throughout the assessment process and is available in the Rating Repository for reading and download (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1: XR4Human Code of Conduct with four guided steps to support implementation

The screenshot shows the XR4Human Code of Conduct website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for Home, Experiences, Deliverables, Rating Repository, Forum, Our Team, News, and social media icons for X and LinkedIn. The main heading is "XR4Human Code of Conduct". Below this, it indicates "Version 1.0" and "Code of Conduct for the Human-Centered and Ethical Development of Immersive Technologies". A "Download" button is visible. A "Table of Contents" section lists various articles, including Preamble, Scope, Guiding Principles, and seven numbered articles covering topics like User Transparency, Data Protection, Risk Management, Well-being, Identity, Shared Spaces, and Engagement with Non-Human Resources. The "Preamble" section is expanded, showing text that defines the Code's purpose and scope, emphasizing ethical obligations and human rights.

Figure 2: XR4Human Code of Conduct accessible directly on the website or as download

3 Guided steps for the Rating Repository (WP5)

The XR4Human Rating Repository is structured around four main steps that guide users through the XR4Human Rating System, as illustrated in Figure 3.

The four steps: Learn, Assess, Test & Explore, and Reflect, emerged from iterative discussions on how to best support developers and users in understanding and applying the XR4Human Code of Conduct (D5.2).

Learn: The users are in the first step invited to explore the XR4Human Code of Conduct along with foundational resources such as the educational toolbox, publications, and project reports. This step establishes the ethical and legal context for XR development.

Assess: In the second step, developers are recommended to evaluate their XR project ideas using the Ethical Impact Assessment and the XR4Human Compliance Checklist. These tools help identify ethical risks and guide necessary adjustments to align with the XR4Human Code of Conduct.

Test & Explore: Developers are in the third step encouraged to pilot their ideas where possible, use the Experience Library for inspiration, and gather feedback from end users to refine concepts and improve inclusivity.

Reflect: The fourth and final step promotes critical reflection on the development process and outcomes. It encourages sharing insights within the XR4Human Forum to foster collective learning and continuous improvement.

The four steps were defined during the design phase to translate the conceptual goals of the Rating Repository into a practical, user-friendly framework, with each step corresponding to specific contributions from partners and deliverables.

The development process unfolded in three phases.

1. Designing the Rating Repository structure: defining the four steps and overall layout.
2. Collecting feedback: via a workshop and questionnaire shared with all partners.
3. Integration and enrichment: incorporating partner suggestions and adding material from deliverables into the thematic sections and AI guide.

Contributions from each work package were aligned with the steps.

Figure 3: Four guided steps designed to support ethical implementation in XR development

4.1 Learn

The first guided step, *Learn*, focusing on understanding ethical, legal, and interoperability principles, provides links to the first four thematic sections (Figure 4):

- Educational Toolbox
- Ethics
- Interoperability
- Legal/Policy

Figure 4: An overview of the Thematic Sections of the Rating Repository

4.1.1. Educational Toolbox (WP7)

The aim of the Educational Toolbox (D7.3; Figure 5) is to empower European citizens by providing clear and accessible information about XR applications, enabling them to make informed choices tailored to their specific needs.

The three objectives of the Educational Toolbox are:

1. To further familiarize end users with the essential terminology surrounding immersive technologies.
2. To raise awareness of the ethical and practical risks associated with XR, such as data privacy, accessibility challenges, and interoperability issues.
3. To advocate for responsible XR use, providing users with practical guidelines and strategies to make informed and safe choices when engaging with XR technologies.

The Educational Toolbox methodology (D7.3) is based on literature review and mapping exercises.

The three educational videos provide information on:

- Familiarizing with XR technology: Starting from the basics
- Bridging the Gaps: The Imperative for Responsible XR Technologies
- Emerging Frameworks for human-centered XR EU ecosystem

Figure 5: Educational videos in the Educational Toolbox

4.1.2 Ethics (WP2)

The Ethics thematic section (Figure 6) builds on the objectives of the XR4Human Ethics work package (D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4), aiming to ensure ethical and inclusive XR development by assessing frameworks, identifying risks and dilemmas, and providing recommendations for a comprehensive code of conduct.

The objectives are:

1. To provide an overview of and assess relevant ethical frameworks, codes of conduct, and good practices
2. To identify various forms of risk and harm relevant to XR
3. To identify moral dilemmas and suitable models of harm
4. To identify and address ethical issues beyond risk, harm, and safety

The methodology for the thematic section on ethics includes a combination of approaches: literature reviews, qualitative content analysis, phenomenological analysis, applied ethics,

reflective equilibrium method, multi-stakeholder interviews, thematic analysis, and comparative policy and ethics review.

A variety of resources grouped into two categories – Mapping and Recommendations – are provided with detailed explanations as well as links to the related deliverables.

Figure 6: Ethics mapping and recommendation resources

4.1.3 Interoperability (WP4)

The aim of the Interoperability guide (D4.1; Figure 7) is to provide an overview of the current state of interoperability, existing and emerging standards, guidelines, surveys frameworks, white papers, and best practices related to XR and spatial computing.

The objectives are:

1. To map the current state of Interoperability in XR, from an XR infrastructure perspective, platforms, and systems

2. To create awareness of lack and limitations of interoperability in the XR and spatial computing community/Industry and how this affects the development of XR solutions as well as accessibility.
3. To assess whether interoperability affects accessibility in XR and spatial computing.
4. To assess the existing state/landscape of interoperability within XR and spatial computing.
5. To identify, address and identify issues/challenges and emerging requirements.

The Interoperability guide methodology is based on literature review and mapping exercises.

Mapping resources with detailed explanations and links to related deliverables are provided (Figure 7).

The screenshot shows the XR4 HUMAN website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: Home, Experiences, Deliverables, Rating Repository, Forum, Our Team, News, and social media icons for X and LinkedIn. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column is titled 'Aim' and contains the text: 'The aim is to provide an overview of the current state of interoperability, existing and emerging standards, guidelines, surveys frameworks, white papers, and best practices related to XR and spatial computing.' The right column is titled 'Objectives' and contains a bulleted list:

- Map the current state of Interoperability in XR, from an XR Infrastructure perspective, platforms, and systems
- Create awareness of lack and limitations of interoperability in the XR and spatial computing community/Industry and how this affects the development of XR solutions as well as accessibility.
- Assess whether Interoperability affects accessibility in XR and spatial computing. Specific Objectives:
 - To assess the existing state/landscape of Interoperability within XR and spatial computing
 - To identify, address and identify issues/challenges and emerging requirements.

Below these sections, there is a 'Methodology' section with the text: 'Literature review, Mapping exercise'. At the bottom, there is a 'Resources' section featuring a purple card with a mapping icon and the text: 'Map existing and emerging requirements for interoperability in X...'. A large 'T' watermark is visible on the left side of the screenshot.

Figure 7: Interoperability mapping resources

4.1.4 Legal/Policy (WP3)

The Legal/Policy thematic session (Figure 8) builds on the objectives of the XR4Human work package 3 (D3.1, D3.2), aiming to examine, evaluate, and provide guidance on the related regulatory and governance issues arising in XR technologies.

The objectives are:

1. To map the regulatory and governance landscape in terms of government, industry, and civil society stakeholders
2. To analyse the current state-of-art in European policy and governance discussions on XR technologies
3. To analyse the current state-of-art in the regulatory landscape relevant to XR technologies
4. To identify governance and regulatory gaps in terms of benefits, risks and impacts associated with XR technologies

The methodology is based on literature review.

Mapping resources with detailed explanations and links to related deliverables are provided.

Figure 8: Legal and regulatory gaps resources

4.2 Assess

The second guided step, Assess, aims to the application of practical tools in development of XR applications and provides links to the following tools: the XR4Human Ethical Impact Assessment and the Code of Conduct Compliance Checklist.

4.2.1 Ethical Impact Assessment (WP5)

The XR4human Ethical Impact Assessment for Immersive Technologies aims to provide a structured framework for developers to assess, anticipate, and mitigate the effects of their

innovations on users, society, and the environment (D5.2; Figure 9). The Ethical Impact Assessment serves as an essential tool for evaluating the ethical implications of immersive experiences, including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR) based on the outlined principles and articles of the XR4human Code of Conduct for developers/users.

There are five key areas of impact:

1. Health and Wellbeing
2. Autonomy and Identity
3. Data and Technology
4. Social
5. Environmental

The corresponding guiding principles and relevant articles from the XR4Human Code of Conduct are noted under each area of impact. The developer is encouraged to read the Code of Conduct before going through the questions in this impact assessment. Following this assessment, developers are encouraged to complete the XR4Human Compliance Checklist to ensure all areas have been considered.

This deliverable is awaiting approval from the European Commission

Overview

The XR4human Ethical Impact Assessment (EIA) for Immersive Technologies aims to provide a structured framework for developers to assess, anticipate, and mitigate the effects of their innovations on users, society, and the environment. The ethics impact assessment serves as an essential tool for evaluating the ethical implications of immersive experiences, including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR) based on the outlined principles and articles of the XR4human Code of Conduct for developers/users. There are five (5) key areas of impact: Health and wellbeing, Autonomy and identity, Data and Technology, Social, and Environmental. The corresponding guiding principles and relevant articles from the [XR4Human Code of Conduct](#) are noted under each area of impact. The developer is encouraged to read the [Code of Conduct](#) before going through the questions in this impact assessment. Following this assessment, developers are encouraged to complete the checklist to ensure all areas have been considered.

XR4Human Code of Conduct Principles

Five Key Areas of Impact

- Health & Wellbeing
 - Human-Centred Design
 - Diversity, Inclusivity, Accessibility & Equitability
 - Safe Experience
 - Sustainability
- Autonomy & Identity
 - Identity & Right to Anonymity
 - Trustworthiness & Transparency
- Social
 - Privacy & Data Governance
- Data & Technology
 - Technical Security & Interoperability
 - Moral Dilemma Resolution & Risk Management
- Environmental

Download the Impact Assessment document:

[Download](#)

Figure 9: Ethical Impact Assessment

4.2.2 XR4Human Compliance Checklist (WP5)

The XR4Human Compliance Checklist (D5.2; Figure 10) is designed to help assess compliance with the principles and articles of the XR4Human Code of Conduct. Before using this checklist for review, it is recommended to review the Code of Conduct and complete the Ethical Impact Assessment.

Home Experiences Deliverables Rating Repository Forum Our Team News [X](#) [in](#)

XR4Human Compliance Checklist

The XR4HUMAN Human-Centered and Ethical Development of Immersive Technologies Checklist is designed to help assess compliance with the principles and articles of the Code of Conduct. For more precise references and guidance, please consult the Code of Conduct directly. Before using this checklist for review, it is recommended to review the [Code of Conduct](#) and complete the [ethical impact assessment](#).

Key Areas of Impact	Yes	No	In part	N/A	Evidence / Notes to indicate criterion to satisfied
1. Health and Wellbeing					
Principles: Human-Centered Design Articles: Wellbeing by Design					
The XR experience was developed through iterative user testing and ethical design principles, ensuring that it aligns with human-centered design criteria by prioritizing usability and user well-being (physical and mental).					
2. Autonomy and Identity					
Principles: Human-Centered Design, Identity and right to anonymity, Trustworthiness and Transparency Articles: User Transparency by Design, Identity, Engagement with Non-Human Resources					
The XR experience was designed to authentically represent user identities while upholding autonomy, ensuring that users have full control over their presence, choices, and interactions within the immersive environment.					
3. Data and Technology					
Principles: Trustworthiness and Transparency, Privacy and Data governance, Technical security and interoperability Articles: Data gathering protection and use					
Privacy and Data Governance: The XR experience was developed with robust data protection measures and adherence to legal and ethical data governance frameworks, ensuring user privacy, informed consent, and secure handling of personal data.					
Interoperability: The XR experience was developed with consideration of interoperability to facilitate seamless integration across platforms where practicable.					
Technical security: Technical security measures include robust cybersecurity measures to protect user data and system integrity.					
4. Social					
Principles: Diversity, inclusivity and accessibility, Equitability, Safe Experience, Risk Management and Moral Dilemma Resolution Articles: Shared Spaces, Engagement with Non-Human Resources					
Equitability and Diversity: The XR experience was developed with a commitment to social equity, ensuring fair representation, inclusive design, and equitable access to immersive technologies for diverse users, where practicable.					
Accessibility and Inclusivity: The XR experience was designed with accessibility and inclusivity at its core, incorporating adaptive features, diverse user needs, and compliance with accessibility standards to facilitate equitable participation for all users.					
5. Environmental					
Principles: Sustainability Articles: Risk Management by Design					
The XR experience was developed with sustainability in mind, incorporating energy-efficient technologies, eco-friendly design practices, and responsible resource engagement to minimize environmental impact.					

[Download](#)

Figure 10: XR4Human Compliance Checklist

4.3 Test & Explore

4.3.1 Experience Library (WP6)

The third guided step, Test & Explore, provides the direct link to the XR4Human Experience Library (Task 6.2; Figure 11, 12), which can also be accessed through the Thematic sections. The XR4Human team launched a curated library that hosts eXtended Reality (XR) experiences. The goal of the Experience Library is to empower the community to highlight their commitment to best practices by sharing their own XR experiences (which may include applications, games, tools and assets) that community members can use, enjoy, adapt and integrate into their own work.

As a Horizon-funded platform, EU-funded XR projects are strongly encouraged to showcase their outputs through the library. Each submission is tagged, making it easy to search and sort by key criteria, such as technology type, required hardware, domain focus, and user experience level. Members of the wider community are also invited to join and share their XR experiences,

fostering a collaborative environment dedicated to pushing the boundaries of immersive technologies.

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Figure 11: The XR4Human Experience Library applications

Figure 12: Experience Library User Guide

4.4 Reflect

4.4.1 Forum (WP1)

The final guided step, Reflect, includes the link to the XR4Human Forum (Task 1.2; Figure 13). The XR4Human Forum is a place for community discussions about the personal and societal risks and opportunities presented by virtual worlds and XR technologies.

The Forum objectives are:

1. To facilitate open dialogue between diverse stakeholders on the personal and societal risks and opportunities of virtual worlds and XR technologies.
2. To promote awareness about the ethical, legal, and societal implications of XR by fostering conversations around key challenges and opportunities.
3. To identify emerging issues in XR, providing insights to inform research, policy, and industry practices, while fostering inclusivity to ensure all voices and diverse perspectives are heard and valued.

The Forum methodology is based on needs assessment and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 13: Link to XR4Human Forum

The XR4Human Forum is organized in 4 categories (Figure 14, 15):

- Ethical Frameworks for XR and Virtual Worlds
- Experience Library
- Regulatory Gap Analysis
- XR Code of Conduct

Figure 14: XR4Human Forum categories

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Figure 15: XR4Human Forum: Categories and user topics

4 Tools

Three tools to support the implementation of the XR4Human Code of Conduct are provided in the Rating Repository: (1) the XR4Human Compliance Checklist, (2) the Ethical Impact Assessment, and (3) the AI Guide (Figure 16). The first two tools are described above, in the context of the second guided step Assess.

The third tool, the AI Guide, is designed to provide guiding prompts to help users extract and combine knowledge from the XR4Human deliverables with their own documents using a large language model (LLM) of their choice.

Figure 16: Rating Repository Tools

5.1 AI Guide (WP7)

The AI Guide (Figure 17) provides a prompt library categorized by XR4Human work package topics (see Appendix 1). These initial prompts are intended to guide stakeholders to start eliciting knowledge from the XR4Human Code of Conduct and other deliverables and documents.

The XR4Human knowledge base can be blended with stakeholders’ own documents, and the initial XR4Human prompts can be used together with more complex prompts in stakeholders’ LLM tools of their choice.

It would further benefit the European XR ecosystem if the XR4Human Code of Conduct and other XR4Human deliverables were integrated into the chapters of the EU AI Act (as outlined in The AI Act Explorer | EU Artificial Intelligence Act) within an information system. This would enable stakeholders to create complex prompts tailored to their specific characteristics, aligning with the EU AI Act Explorer and the EU AI Act Compliance Checker. These prompts could account for factors such as entity type, AI-XR integration type, XR type (hardware/software), XR safety aspects, mission, user categories, desired outcomes, and more.

Figure 17: Rating Repository AI Guide

All XR4Human deliverables are available in the dedicated 'Deliverables' section (Figure 18). They can be consulted, downloaded and integrated in stakeholders' personal or enterprise information systems for further processing and prompting.

Figure 18: XR4Human deliverables to be used as a knowledge base in an AI prompting application

5 Thematic Sections

The Rating Repository contains six thematic sections (Figure 18):

- Interoperability
- Ethics
- Legal/Policy
- Education
- Experience Library
- Forum

Figure 19: Thematic sections of the Rating Repository

The structure of the first four thematic sections – *Interoperability*, *Ethics*, *Legal/Policy*, and *Education* – is as follows:

- **Level 1:** Presents the aims, objectives, and methodology of the thematic area.
- **Level 2:** Offers “building blocks” of information. In *Interoperability*, *Ethics*, and *Legal/Policy*, these focus on Mapping and Recommendations. In *Education*, an educational toolbox of videos is provided to support learning and empower end users to make informed decisions.
- **Level 3:** Provides detailed and enriched content drawn from XR4Human deliverables, including studies, tables and multimedia materials.

This approach across the four sections allows users to progress from general overview to more detailed insights.

The remaining two thematic sections – *the XR4Human Experience Library* and *XR4Human Forum* – feature a structure tailored to the specific objectives they serve.

6 Conclusion

The XR4Human Rating Repository provides a knowledge base with a comprehensive set of resources, including guidelines and tools, designed to facilitate the implementation of the XR4Human Code of Conduct and to support a variety of XR stakeholders in conducting ethical assessments within XR contexts.

Both practical mapping and complete references to XR4Human deliverables are provided for helping stakeholders to carry out their XR ethical assessment processes in a staged approach.

The XR4Human Rating Repository, Code of Conduct, and ethics deliberation processes are designed to align with the evolving convergence of extended reality (XR)/virtual worlds and artificial intelligence (AI). As the integration of AI, generative AI, and XR/virtual worlds progresses, it is essential to harmonize the requirements, tools, and needs of both XR and AI technologies. This approach aims to empower European stakeholders in addressing ethics-related challenges and opportunities within XR-AI initiatives to foster the growth and sustainability of the European XR ecosystem.

This deliverable is awaiting approval from the European Commission

7 Appendix 1: Sample XR4Human Prompts

The following prompts were provided by the XR4Human team members involved in the various work packages.

WP2: Ethics guidelines for XR technologies

What are the relevant values and principles in existing ethics guidelines, codes for immersive or XR technologies?

What are the physical risks of XR?

What are the psychological risks of XR?

What are the societal risks of XR?

What are possible mitigation strategies to address ethical issues of XR technologies?

What are the main categories of risks associated with XR technologies?

What health and wellbeing risks should XR users be aware of?

How might XR technologies impact user autonomy or privacy?

What are the potential psychological or social effects of using XR?

What safety precautions are recommended for XR users?

What are the implications of biometric data collection in XR applications?

What ethical considerations are essential to protect users in XR experiences?

How can designers ensure XR experiences are inclusive and accessible to vulnerable populations?

What is moral programming?

What is the relevance of moral programming for XR technologies?

How can moral programming be integrated into XR technologies?

WP3: Regulations & Governance

Which are the main regulations covering XR developments?

What are the legal rights of XR users?

Which laws govern the development of XR devices?

As an XR developer, which legislation is important to know?

What are the legal particularities for XR devices used in the medical field?

What are the consumer rights for people using XR devices?

Is bullying and cybercrime in virtual reality controlled by the law?

How is the law protecting children using virtual reality?

Do avatars have rights?

What laws govern buying and selling in virtual reality?

WP4: Interoperability

What does interoperability mean within the context of XR and Spatial Computing?

What are the emerging interoperability requirements for XR and Spatial Computing defined by XR4HUMAN Interoperability Guideline?

What are existing and emerging standards pushing interoperability for XR and Spatial Computing?

What is the current state of interoperability within XR and Spatial Computing?

What are the existing gaps of interoperability?

Why should we leverage interoperability?

Why should I adopt the interoperability guideline?

As a [my organization type/my role] how can I update the interoperability guideline?

What are the gaps within interoperability for XR and Spatial Computing defined by XR4HUMAN Interoperability Guideline?

WP5: Code of Conduct

What is the XR4Human Code of Conduct, and why was it created?

Who is the XR4Human Code of Conduct intended for, and how should it be used?

What are the guiding principles outlined in the XR4Human Code of Conduct?

How does the XR4Human Code of Conduct support ethical decision-making in XR development?

What does “User Transparency by Design” mean in XR, and how can it be implemented?

How can “Data Protection and Privacy by Design” be ensured in immersive environments?

What does “Risk Management by Design” look like in XR applications?

How can XR technologies be designed to promote “Well-being by Design”?

What is a respectful and responsible way to use and represent identity, avatars, and personas in XR environments?

How should developers approach shared spaces and interactions with non-human agents in XR?

WP6: Experience Library

How do I submit an XR experience to the XR4HUMAN Experience Library?

What are the eligibility criteria for the XR4HUMAN Experience Library?

What are benefits of listing my XR project to the XR4HUMAN Experience Library?

What happens after I submit my project to the XR4HUMAN Experience Library?

How do I update or withdraw from the XR4HUMAN Experience Library?

How can I see examples of XR experiences that meet XR4HUMAN's evaluation standards?

This deliverable is awaiting approval from the European Commission